

THE ETIQUETTE OF USING LULLABIES AND OLANS IN THE SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION OF GIRLS

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Abstract. *The subject of this article "Sharqona - the etiquette of using alla and olan in female education" is an extremely relevant situation for family education, which is the basis of society. The issue of women and girls, gender equality, mother's place in society, their manners of education using the alla and ola typical of Eastern women is one of the most important issues in preparing our students for family. attempted. In its content, information is given about the preparation of our future mothers for life and the correct performance of their tasks in raising children.*

Keywords: *family, mother, alla, ulan, personality - social relations, eastern woman, manners of behavior and communication, use of alla and olan, education, girls-women are patient, tolerant, cultured, ibo-imaginary, dignified, proud. and thrifty, intelligent, polite, sweet. willing, exemplary, is a guarantee of family stability.*

"Politeness is a crown, shine from the divine light,
Wear this crown, all roads are open to you"

Jalolidin Rumi.

The state policy aimed at strengthening the family institution in our country, strengthening the importance of family values, and forming intellectual and moral capital in children in order to form the manners of using alla and olan in providing spiritual and moral education to female students, the goal of moral and moral education of male and female students expands the possibility of implementation. Also, the need to develop the effectiveness of the system of spiritual and moral upbringing of children in the family on the basis of the cooperation mechanism of the family-neighborhood-preschool educational institution is becoming urgent.

No matter what aspect of the development of today's society, man is its active participant and creator. Among them, women have their own place and potential. We cannot imagine our life without women, women or our mothers. Therefore, today, women are the founders and managers of education and training, and in all processes, women are the leaders and leaders of this activity.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, paid special attention to the role of women and showed the creation of all the necessary conditions for the development of their activities in the society, for directing their talents and abilities to the interests of the country. In this regard, the role of the Women's Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been further increased. To increase the socio-political and social activity of women in our country, to create conditions for them to realize their abilities and opportunities in various fields and industries, to ensure unconditional observance of their rights and legal interests, to protect motherhood and childhood Wide-scale work is being carried out to provide support, as well as to strengthen the institution of the family.

In the **introduction** to today's topic, we consider the issue of women and girls, gender equality, and the role of the mother in society to be one of the most important issues, and we will definitely try to explain this issue based on complete examples. We believe that it is very difficult

to imagine human life without a mother, the development of society without a woman, and the family atmosphere without our daughters. I hope that we will try to provide enough information in the specific content of the topic, to prepare our daughters for life and to help future mothers to perform their duties in child-rearing correctly, understanding the great responsibility they face.

The **main goal** of the article is to educate our future mothers, that is, our daughters, who are entering the society, using the virtues and virtues of national values.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", No. PF-5325 of February 2, 2018 "Supporting Women and Girls Decrees of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 19, 2017 No. 528 "On improving the activities of preschool educational institutions" this research serves to a certain extent in the implementation of the tasks defined in the decision and other regulatory legal documents.

Focusing on **the theoretical aspects** of the article, children's education has acquired a historical character as a problem, and scientific and didactic works created by such thinkers as Unsurlmaoli Kaikovus, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Mahmud Kashgari, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur. sources are important in education.

In this regard, D. Abdurahimova, M. Inomova, V. Karimova, M. Mahmudova, O. Musurmonova, A. Mukhsiyeva, N. Ortikov, M. Salayeva, H. J. Khudoykulov, M. Umarova, O'. Shamsiyev, Sh. Shodmonova, M.Yakubbekova, M.Kuronov's scientific works researched spirituality, morals, national pride, culture formation in children and adolescents, the role of parents' relationship in the upbringing of a child's personality, poetic peculiarities of all.

The main theoretical aspects of the subject are that human relations are processes of interaction in which interpersonal relations are formed, and in this regard, the communication education of girls and future mothers entering the society is of particular importance. Among them, Allah and Ulan are important. Every people, nation has its own culture, traditions and values, which definitely affects the upbringing of the young generation entering the society. It is necessary for the girls of our Uzbek nation to be educated in Eastern communication in every household, because our girls are future mothers.

It is appropriate to pay attention to the following tasks in order to form the manners of using alla and olan in providing spiritual and moral education to female students:

- to interpret the socio-ideological content of allas, educational influence, the etymological meaning and historical formation of the word alla from a pedagogical point of view, and to analyze the philosophical, pedagogical and psychological situation of spiritual and moral education of children through the means of alla;

- classification of alla types aimed at spiritual and moral education according to the didactic content of children's age, psychological and spiritual development;

- improvement of the socio-pedagogical mechanism of increasing the efficiency of spiritual and moral upbringing of children by means of alla on the basis of family-neighborhood-preschool educational institution cooperation;

- development of recommendations aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the method of spiritual and moral upbringing of children by means of alla.

The following are of special importance for the formation of the etiquette of using alla and olan in providing spiritual and moral education to female students:

- the content of educational formation of alla (the etymology of the word alla "balu-balu", "allala", "alang", "ala" depends on phonetic changes) historical, encyclopedic, pedagogical-psychological and folk language determined on the basis of giving priority to the activating, motivational components of the epistemological methods used in preparing children for social life in the sources of Zaki's work;

- characteristics of children's psychological and spiritual development with the help of alla (from infancy to three years of caressing, pampering; from three years of age guiding to goodness, advice; from four years of age guided to dreams and hopes; didactic allas of five years of age) all types of didactic, logical, innovative principles are defined in harmony;

The mechanism of organization and conduct of spiritual and moral activities by means of alla in the cooperation of family-neighborhood-preschool educational institution, visual-active thinking, synchronous effect of alla (phonemic sounds) and alla of folk oral creativity, proverb, improved on the basis of giving priority to sub-genres such as riddle, matal, quick telling, fairy tale;

indicators of gradual spiritual and moral development of children in the family were improved according to the principles of national and universal values in accordance with the requirements of retrospective periodicity.

The practical results of the article are reflected in the following: based on the integrative coordination of the principles of traditional succession, pedagogical cooperation plans for the activities of the monthly courses "My daughter is important", "Motherhood happiness" were developed;

"Family-neighborhood-preschool educational institution" cooperation system, criteria for spiritual and moral upbringing of children in the family by all means, proposals and recommendations regarding the problems of using educational games, interactive methods and game technologies were developed;

"Cradle the child", "Kulcha dumaltadi", "Duk urdi", "Grandfather drank water", "Alla say, my dear child" in cooperation with the family-neighborhood-preschool educational institution in the spiritual and moral education of children in the family by means of alla. , "My daughter has reached puberty" and "My grandmother says so" educational events and competitions were introduced;

- on the basis of the recommendations developed according to the scientific results of the research, the activities of the Republican "Alla House" cultural and educational community center were improved;

- the criteria for determining the level of knowledge, skills, and abilities of mothers in raising children with the help of alla, the level of spiritual and moral education of children and its indicators were developed;

"Pedagogical-organizational structure of the process of spiritual and moral education of children in the family by means of alla", in spiritual and moral education of children by means of alla for family-neighborhood-preschool educational institution

Preparing our daughters who are coming into life to become mothers in the future is to prepare them to be a role model as a virtuous, dignified, proud, thrifty and intelligent mother in accordance with our national values. It is said that "the equality of genes in the society, the activeness of our daughters, showing their activity in life no less than anyone else, it is the happiness of the family, the prosperity of the neighborhood and the prosperity of the country."

Therefore, the education of girls is a very sensitive issue, neglecting it can cause huge problems. Every parent wants their daughter to be a good person, to be the owner of the honorable name "MOTHER" in the society. In our people, they say that there is nothing wrong with a dream, a dream is one thing, practical work is another. In this regard, it is the main duty of each of our daughters, that is, mothers, to communicate beautifully and use *alla* and *olan*.

Saying *Alla* and *Olan* dates back to the thousand-year history of our nation.

Alla jonning rohati, alla...

Allani is initiated by older midwives and continued by young people. For example, eighty-five-year-old Onakhon Momo Akramova straightens a white shawl as if she were preparing to face her face on the congratulatory altar:

Bismillah Rahmani Rohiyim!

Mom is about to start, but my tongue suddenly wakes up. A funny, painful, medicinal voice begins:

God bless you, God bless you,

I'm going to lift it up and do it

If my God spares your life, I spare my life.

Educate and become mullahs, God bless you...

So simple, magical, loving... the instruments are silent... the words have a trembling heart.

There are countless competitions, contests, and debates held in Tashkent. There is no doubt that the audition of *Alla* performers is one of the most attractive and unique events of our year. The main slogans are as follows:

Do you get daily updates on how your mother is doing? Did you go far away in search of happiness or in the arms of the winds of fate? When was the last time you lost your mother? When you go, you will only show your height and forget about your successes and failures. Will you have time to look into the eyes of your parents, to talk to them, and to follow them and tell them your dreams like you did in your younger years? Today, each of us is looking for a soul that understands our language and heart. And our mothers have never found a better confidant than us since the day we were born. I feel this truth clearly when I listen to Allah.

O my God, the language of your power, Allah,

A child is the fruit of this world.

A child is the fruit of this world.

Long live the rich country - that's all...

I don't know how much the order and details of this wonderful conference, which was attended by little girls and children whose tongues are still slurred, to mothers who are reaching the end of their lives, I don't know, but the more I listen to some examples of the Gods scattered in the bosom of Uzbekistan, polished by our grandmothers over the centuries, my soul, my tongue I felt that his eyes were shining. A friend of mine said: "When I was little, I fell asleep listening to my mother's music, and when I grew up, I would be haunted by it."

If I put my hand on my chest, honey, oh

I have a heart, I don't have a liver, I'm lonely, *alla*,

If I remember the past, my lamb, *alla*,

I don't have a place in this world.

The legacy of mothers who wish only happiness, peace, and joy to their offspring. Do not look for the answer to this question in the social order of the past. Allah is the divine power

eternally victorious over the big and small stages of history, revolutions, rulings and decrees - the expression of mothers' life born anew on the border of Dream and Dream.

Hello, hello, I love you, hello,
Come on, don't complain to God, oh God,
I'm complaining
Oh, I'm begging you, God alone.

About the sanctity of the mother and the duties of children, hundreds of thousands of copies of newspapers and magazines are being preached by wordsmiths. But why is the number of childless children increasing by the hour?

A girl is a stone of destiny. A woman gnaws when there is water in the rozgor, and gnaws when there is a stone. The mother increases the good of the house, hides the bad, and wins the sales. According to modern psychologists, there is a limit to suffering and suffering. At such times, there is nothing better than Allah:

My father was like a great mountain, my mother was like a flowing garden, my God.
Every word is like butter, God, Death broke my neck, God.

Onakhan, the oldest participant of the pageant, said:

I had only one son left when he died, and he accidentally left me in this world at a young age. My daughter-in-law also moved to her mother's place, leaving two of her four children to me. Crying and crying after my son...

I'll find you, baby
If I look for mountain stones, my dear child, alla.
I'll burn a bunch of herbs, bye-bye,
My dear, if only I could see it.

Hey! In old age, who will understand the plight of a poor old man whose heart trembles in the worry of living, as if he had been burned on the spot of a child, and who will spare him? Are there many or few of them around us? Our mothers and fathers, whose hearts are the treasure of national creativity, while keeping the rusty horseshoe of the horses of the peoples who cherished their value, put them on a seven-layer blanket, and put the jewels of their hearts. can't we pick one?

During the inspection days, watching the audience gathered on the angelic, beautiful, miraculous stage of the madrasa - mainly people related to art and culture, not a single dream left my tongue:

I wish that the performances of these Gods, which are meaningful, unique, and instructive, would move to large stages and neighborhoods, and that mothers, daughters-in-law, daughters would see and learn from them... If only these natural, beautiful Gods would be used...

In conclusion, we would like to say that if the girls who are entering each society use the Eastern customs, alla and olan to form education and manners of communication and communication, their life will be pleasant and happy. Because the most valuable thing in the communication process is the communication itself. The listener gets useful information from good dialogue. That is why it is necessary for our girls to learn the etiquette of using alla and olan in the education of Eastern women.

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